

OPTIMIZATION OF TACTICS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF OSTEOVASCULAR INJURIES OF THE LIMB WITH CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract. *In this article, the authors present research data on the diagnosis and optimization of tactics for surgical treatment of osteovascular injuries with consequences. 22 patients with combined osteovascular injuries were observed (4 - consequences). Among the victims: 19 (86.3); men and 3 (13.6%) aged 10 to 70 years. Patients of working age 70%. For bone fractures and limb ischemia, ultrasound, radiocontrast angiography and MSCT were used. Results. In 3 cases, we used osteosynthesis for bone fractures. For 11 wounds with bone fractures without displacement of the fragments, we considered it appropriate to apply a plaster cast. Skeletal retraction was performed in 3 patients.*

Keywords: *osteovascular injuries, diagnostics, endovascular and surgical treatment.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье авторами приведены данные исследования диагностики и оптимизации тактики хирургического лечения костно-сосудистых повреждений с последствиями. Под наблюдением находились 22 пациента с сочетанными костно-сосудистыми повреждениями (4 - последствия). Среди пострадавших: 19 (86,3); мужчины и 3 (13,6%) в возрасте от 10 до 70 лет. Пациенты трудоспособного возраста 70%. При переломах костей и ишемии конечностей применяли УЗИ, рентгеноконтрастную ангиографию и МСКТ. Результаты. В 3 случаях при переломах костей мы применили остеосинтез. При 11 ранах с переломами костей без смещения отломков мы сочли целесообразным наложить гипсовую повязку. Скелетная ретракция выполнена 3 пациентам.*

Ключевые слова: *костно-сосудистые повреждения, диагностика, эндоваскулярное и хирургическое лечение.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada mualliflar oqibatlariga olib keladigan osteovaskulyar shikastlanishlarni jarrohlik davolash taktikasini tashxislash va optimallashtirish bo'yicha tadqiqot ma'lumotlarini taqdim etadilar. Kombinatsiyalangan osteo-qon tomir shikastlanishi bo'lgan 22 bemor kuzatildi (4 - oqibatlar). Jabrlanganlar orasida: 19 (86,3); erkaklar va 3 (13,6%) 10 yoshdan 70 yoshgacha. Mehnat yoshidagi bemorlar 70%. Suyak sinishi va oyoq-qo'l ishemiyasi uchun ultratovush, radiokonstrastli angiografiya va MSCT ishlatilgan. Natijalar. 3 holatda biz suyak sinishi uchun osteosintezdan foydalandik. Suyak sinishi bo'lgan 11 ta jarohatlar bo'laklari joyidan siljimasdan, biz gipsni qo'llashni to'g'ri deb hisobladik. 3 bemorda skelet retraksiyasi amalga oshirildi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *suyak-tomir shikastlanishlari, diagnostika, endovaskulyar va jarrohlik davolash.*

Introduction. Timely diagnostics and optimization of surgical treatment tactics for patients with combined bone and vascular injuries remains one of the pressing problems of modern vascular surgery [1]. This problem arose at the intersection of traumatology and vascular surgery.

Currently, there is an increase in injuries associated with a sharp increase in transport vehicles, increased speeds, intensification of labor and scientific and technological progress.

In peacetime, about 0.3% of all traumatic injuries are associated with vessels and up to 17.5% - gunshot wounds [2]. It has been established that in 2% of patients, open fractures are accompanied by damage to the main vessels [3,4,5]. Vascular injuries are considered severe injuries, due to the high frequency of complications and fatal outcomes reaching, according to various sources, from 15.4-25.5% [6]. 613 patients with vascular injuries were admitted to the clinic. The majority of victims were diagnosed with combined vascular injury: damage to the artery and veins - 28.3%; vessels and nerves - 28.8%; vessels and bones - 14.4% [3]. The frequency of amputations after combined injury, due to the development of gangrene and crushing of soft tissues, ranges from 20 to 40% [7].

With combined injury and decompensation of blood circulation, the risk of developing thrombotic and purulent-necrotic complications increases sharply [3].

With bone fractures, the total number of vascular injuries increases significantly and ranges from 20-31.25%, which occur during military operations and 2-10.5%, in peacetime [8].

The purpose of this study is to study the clinical course and diagnosis of bone and vascular injuries, determine the optimization of the surgical recovery option and the sequence of their implementation. This work is devoted to the analysis of the results of the experience of surgical treatment of bone and vascular injuries with consequences.

Material and methods. We observed 22 patients with combined bone and vascular injuries (4 with sequelae) (mean age 28.62 ± 9.09 , $p > 0.05$). Upon admission to the clinic, the patients' condition was as follows: extremely severe - 1 (4.5%); severe - 10 (45.4%); moderate - 5 (22.7%) and satisfactory - 6 (27). Among the victims there were: 86.3% men and 3 (13.6%), aged 10-70 years and patients of working age - 70%. Days of hospitalization: 23.27 ± 13.11 , $p < 0.05$. There were 15 such patients (68.2%) admitted to the CG before 2000, and 7 (31.8%) in the MG from 2000-2018, $p < 0.05$. The patients were distributed by age and gender, which are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Distribution of patients by gender and age

Age of patients	Total	Including			
		Men		Women	
		CG	MG	CG	MG
up to 20 years	5 (22.7%)	3 (13.6%)	2 (9%)	-	-
21-30 years old	8 (36.3%)	7 (31.8%)	1 (4.5%)	-	-
31-40 years old	3 (13.6%)	3 (13.6%)	-	-	-
41-50 years old	2 (9%)	1 (4.5%)	-	-	1 (4.5%)
51 and older	4 (18,1%)	-	2 (9%)	1 (4,5%)	1 (4,5%)
Total:	22 (100%)	14 (63.6)	5 (22.7)	1 (4.5)	2 (9.0)

When admitting a patient admitted urgently, special attention was paid to: general condition; traumatic fractures; ruptured arteries; veins, etc. At the same time, the weakening of the

pulse and the decrease in pressure on the arteries were caused by significant bleeding in the areas of damage to the lower third of the shoulder and the middle third of the shin.

Basically, the injuries were multiple: crushed fracture of the shin bones; fracture of the femur and head injuries; fracture of the femur and contusion of the pelvic bones; fracture of the shin and contusion of the foot; fracture of the forearm bones and contusion of the torso; fracture of the shoulder and head injuries; damage to bones and blood vessels by bullet wounds; damage to bones and blood vessels by shot wounds.

The causes of combined bone-vascular injuries and the localization of the injury are presented in TVB.2.

Table 2

Localization of injuries with combined bone-vascular injuries

Localization	Number of patients		Percent %	
	abs	%	cg	Mg
Shoulder	7	31.8	5 (22.7%)	2 (9%)
Subclavian	2	9.0	-	2 (9%)
Hips	3	13.6	2 (9%)	1 (4.5%)
shins	5	22.7	4 (18.1%)	1 (4.5%)
Iliac	1	4.5	1 (4.5%)	-
Elbow dislocation	3	13.6	3 (13.6%)	-
Cervical vertebra	1	4.5	1 (4.5%)	-
Total:	22	100,0	16 (72.7)	6(27,2)

In patients with combined bone and vascular injuries, transverse fracture of tubular bones occurred as a result of a strong blow almost perpendicular to the surface of the limb. As a result, In this case, the fractures were: comminuted, transverse and oblique. Of these, three observed patients had a dislocation and rupture of the elbow joint. As a result of the bone fracture, a false aneurysm developed (Table 3).

Table 3

Nature of the fracture and mechanism of injury

Type of fracture	Number of injuries	Direct	Indirect
Transverse	7 (31.8%)	6 (27.2%)	1 (4.5%)
Splintered	10 (45.4%)	8 (36.3%)	2 (9%)
Oblique	2 (9%)	2 (9%)	-
Dislocation and joint rupture	3 (13.6%)	3 (13.6%)	-
Total:	22 (100%)	19 (86.3%)	3 (13.6%)

As a rule, the mechanism and nature of fractures corresponded to classical descriptions. Most oblique fractures, with indirect impact of the blow. Transverse and comminuted fractures, with direct impact of the impact force.

All difficulties occurred in the treatment of victims with combined bone and vascular injuries. They are associated with the correction of shock, normalization of hemodynamics and on which, basically, the fate of the patient depends. Depending on the condition of the patients, the tactical approach to treatment was individual. Having conducted a thorough clinical study, patients with combined bone and vascular injuries were diagnosed. In this case, we used ultrasound

Doppler imaging, X-ray contrast angiography and MSCT. All of the above, we tried to describe the algorithmic approach in the language of flowcharts.

The complexity of choosing the optimal volume of surgical intervention depends on the patient's condition, the nature of the injuries and the damaging effect of the traumatic agent.

We performed X-ray endovascular temporary complete balloon occlusion of arterial vessels. In this case, a balloon catheter (6x60 mm) was used to expand to complete occlusion and patency of the vessels. Occlusion occurred at a pressure in the balloon of up to 9 atm with an RBP of 10 atm. Contrast Unigeksol-350-100 ml (1 bottle of 100 ml). In this case, 3 thousand IU of heparin were administered.

Fig. 1. Treatment and diagnostic algorithm for bone and vascular injuries of the extremities.

Results

Based on the analysis of patient documents and the severity of the condition when providing first aid before inpatient examination, we established a high frequency of tactical errors, including during transportation. All difficulties in the surgical treatment of patients with combined bone and vascular injuries are associated with the correction of shock and normalization of hemodynamics. Depending on the condition of the patients, the surgical tactical approach was individual.

We believe that in case of bone and vascular injuries, stable fixation of fragments makes it possible to determine the true defect between the ends of the vessels and choose the right option for vascular suture or vascular plasty. Final fixation of the fracture of tubular bones by intramedullary osteosynthesis allows avoiding their repeated injury. In this case, correct repositioning, fixation of bone fragments and protection from infection play an important role.

Many years of experience in surgical treatment of bone fractures have shown instability and a large number of complications during fixation of bone fragments. Based on this, in 3 observations of bone fractures we used osteosynthesis. In 11 injuries with bone fractures without displacement of fragments, we considered it appropriate to apply a plaster cast. Skeletal retraction

was performed in 3 victims. In case of bone and vascular injuries, the following types of operations were performed: bandaging - 1 (9.1%); lateral suture - 5 (22.7%); circular suture - 4 (18.1%); autovenous prosthetics - 5 (22.7%); prosthetics - 1 (4.55%) and other types of operations - 6 (27.2%) patients. The results of treatment of patients with vascular and bone injuries are good - 15 patients (68.1%), satisfactory - 2 (9%); unsatisfactory - 5 (22.7%).

Table 4

Nature of surgery for combined bone and vascular injuries

locale-damage-denia	Operations on vessels							Bone surgery		
	Side seam	Circular seam	Autovena	Prosthesis	Spasm resolution	Amputation	Pereknitting	Gypsum	Skeletal retraction	Osteosynthesis
Region shoulder	2 (9%)	2 (9%)	2 (9%)	1 (4.5%)	-	1 (4.5%)	1 (4.5%)	7 (31.8%)	-	2 (9%)
Region Shin					1 (4.5%)	4 (18%)			1 (4.5%)	
Region Hips		2 (9%)	2 (9%)						2 (9%)	1 (4.5%)
Connect chichnaya region	2 (9%)							2 (9%)		
Suspension doshnaya region			1 (4.5%)					1 (4.5%)		
cervical region	1 (4.5%)							1 (4.5%)		
Total:	5 (22.7%)	4 (18%)	5 (22.7%)	1 (4.5%)	1 (4.5%)	5 (22.7%)	1 (4.5%)	11 (50%)	3 (13.6%)	3 (13.6%)

For the prevention of thrombosis and wound infection before, during and after surgery, we prescribed: fresh frozen plasma 5 to 15 ml / kg), heparin from 150 to 250 U / kg, aspirin 0.5 2 times a day after meals. In severe cases, the following were prescribed: contrical 300,000 U or goredex 20,000 U 2 times a day and broad-spectrum antibiotics. In addition, 4 observed patients developed a post-traumatic complication - false aneurysm.

Below is our clinical observation of surgical treatment of a fracture of the middle third of the left clavicle with a pulsating hematoma of the left subclavian artery.

Patient K. A., 68 years old, case file #1162 (29.02.2018) was admitted on an emergency basis. Complaints about a pulsating formation in the left supraclavicular region, severe pain, limited movement of the limb and general weakness. He has considered himself ill for 2 days. He went to medical institutions. Due to the deterioration of his condition in 2018, he went to the

KBSPM, where after examination by a vascular surgeon he was urgently hospitalized. General condition upon admission, moderate. Normal build. Skin and visible mucous membranes are of normal color. Peripheral lymph nodes are not enlarged. Vesicular breathing in the lungs on both sides, no wheezing. Muffled heart sounds. BP 150/70 mm Hg. Pulse 90 beats per minute, rhythmic. The abdomen is of normal shape, participates in the act of breathing. On palpation, the abdomen is soft, painless in all areas. The liver and spleen are not enlarged. The percussion symptom is negative on both sides. The stool tends to constipate. On examination, both lower limbs are of the same diameter. There is no edema. On the left upper limb, in the area above the collarbone, a pulsating formation measuring 15x12 cm is palpated. A dense and tense formation extends from the left axillary region to the buttock. This formation is mobile and painful. On palpation, systolic tremor is noted. Pulsation is determined at all landmarks. On auscultation, a systolic murmur is heard over the aneurysm. Angiography reveals damage to the subclavian artery of the 2nd segment.

Table 5.

Comparative analysis of the results of operations on localized bone-vascular injuries with consequences

Damage d vessel	Types of operations until 2000 (CG)						Types of operations from 2000-2018 (MG)					
	Later al	Cir cul ar	Aut ovei n	Pros thes is	Am puta tion	Spa sm	Lig atio n	Lat era l	Circ ular	Aut ove in	Am puta tion	Total
Carotid artery	1 (4.5%)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1 (4.5%)
Subclavian artery	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2 (9%)	-	-	-	2 (9%)
Brachial artery	2 (9%)	1 (4.5%)	2 (9%)	1 (4.5%)	1 (4.5%)	-	1 (4.5%)	-	-	1 (4.5%)	-	9 (40%)
iliac artery	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1 (4.5%)	-	1 (4.5%)
Femoral artery	-	2 (9%)	1 (4.5%)	-	-	-	-	-	1 (4.5%)	-	-	4 (18.1%)
Popliteal artery	-	-	-	-	2 (9%)	-	-	-	-	-	-	2 (9%)
Leg arteries	-	-	-	-	1 (4.5%)	1 (4.5%)	-	-	-	-	1 (4.5%)	3 (13.6%)

Total:	3 (13.6 %)	3 (13. 6%))	3 (13. 6%)	1 (4.5 %)	4 (18. 1%)	1 (4.5 %)	1 (4. 5%))	2 (9 %))	1 (4.5 %)	2 (9%)	1 (4.5 %)	22 (100%)
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Diagnosis: Fracture of the middle third of the clavicle on the left. Pulsating hematoma of the left subclavian artery.

At the first stage, drug treatment was carried out. At the second stage, under local anesthesia, the brachial artery was exposed on the left. Transverse arteriotomy and insertion of a catheter for temporary occlusion of the damaged area of the left subclavian artery. Under X-ray control, X-ray endovascular occlusion of the left subclavian artery was performed. The catheter was fixed and the patient was transferred to the operating room.

Under intubation anesthesia, a wide access in the supraclavicular region up to 20 cm long was made. The borders of the pulsating hematoma (hematoma measuring 15x12 cm) located in the supraclavicular region were exposed by sharp and blunt methods. During revision, a blood clot up to 700 ml was found and removed. During revision, an arterial defect measuring 0.5x0.3 cm was detected in segment 2 of the left subclavian artery. The clavicle fracture was fixed and the arterial defect was sutured with a lateral suture. Dry hemostasis. The skin was sutured layer by layer. An aseptic dressing was applied. The patient was discharged in a satisfactory condition.

A follow-up examination of the patient was performed a year later. The condition is satisfactory. There is no pain syndrome, postoperative wounds have no signs of inflammation.

Table 5 presents a comparative analysis of the results by types of operations on damaged vessels and their consequences between the main control groups of patients. Good results were obtained in reconstructive surgeries. At the same time, the number of patients with amputations makes up the majority in the control group. Patients with amputations before 2000 by limbs: brachial artery - 1 (4.5%); popliteal artery - 2 (9%). From 2000-2018, amputations were performed after injury to the artery of the lower leg - 1 (4.5%) patient. In addition, 4 (18.1%) patients developed false aneurysm of the artery: femoral - 2 (9%); subclavian - 2 (9%). The following was performed: lateral suture - 2; circular suture - 1; autovenous stenting - 1. The immediate results were good.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Selection of the optimal surgical tactics, depending on: the patient's condition, the nature of the injury and the damaging effect of the traumatic agent.

2. Determination of the true defect between the ends of the vessels and the choice of the optimal version of the vascular suture or plastic, carried out by stable fixation of fragments of bone and vascular damage.

3. Tactics of surgical treatment (bone and vascular) TAA, are implemented in stages: Stage 1 - drug treatment; Stage 2 - X-ray endovascular method of balloon occlusion of vessels; Stage 3 - selection of the optimal approach to the TAA operation; Stage 4 - elimination of traumatic arterial aneurysm and Stage 5 - fixation of bone fracture by osteosynthesis and surgical reconstruction of the main vessels.

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